

substantial supply of residual moisture and the low initial weed population. Rice was cut close to the ground and gramoxone herbicide was applied. Seed of soybeans and mung beans were dibbled. Plots were weeded twice by hand. Insects were adequately controlled by two sprayings of carbofuran, followed by three sprayings of methomyl whenever initial pest damage was observed.

Varieties that yielded significantly higher than others were soybean Kuro daizu; mung beans CES 1 D-21, E.G. Glabrous #3, CES 55, and Dau Mo; and cowpeas E.G. #3, E.G. #2, and TVu4-b-b-10-b (see table). Yields were almost as high as those of the same crops grown with good tillage under upland conditions. Yields of the high yielding legumes ranged from 4 to 88% higher

than those of the checks. All crops matured within 71 to 81 days; mung beans generally matured earliest, followed by cowpeas, then soybeans. Soybean plants were shorter and matured earlier than usual because of photoperiod reaction. The cowpea crop, which was not mulched, did not grow as tall as mung beans. The mung bean crop, which was mulched, had a better supply of moisture.

A novel strategy of intercropping in traditional lowland rice fields to maximize food production

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Intercropping is well suited for small farmers who seek to maximize production by having one or more crops on every square meter of land all year round. Little work has been done on intercropping in lowland rice fields where the traditional practice is to raise two or more crops of rice in tandem sequence. The feasibility of raising high-value crops in the traditional wetlands was studied during the rabi season (Feb.–May) of 1976–77 at the Rice Research Station, Pattambi.

A rice field of 574.8 sq m was divided into two parts. In one (245.5 sq m), the rice variety Triveni was transplanted. In the other part (329.3 sq m) the intercropping study was conducted. Ash gourd, cucumber, okra, and cowpea were planted on raised beds 16.5 m long, 1.5 m wide, and 10 cm high. The distance between two beds was 2 m. Four such beds occupied 99 sq m. On all sides of the beds, Triveni was transplanted as in the other portion of the field. The net area of rice in the intercropped field was 230.3 sq m.

Cucumber and ash gourd were raised in polythene cups and 18- to 20-day-old seedlings were transplanted in the raised beds immediately after planting rice to reduce the cropping time in the main field. Okra was seeded directly between each two cucumber and ash gourd seedlings. Cowpea was sown on the borders of all beds. Vegetables were not irrigated, as sufficient moisture was

available in their root zones by capillary rise from the rice fields where the soil was kept under shallow submergence (2–5 cm).

The rice crop yielded 107.8 kg grain (4.4 t/ha) and 169.0 kg straw (6.9 t/ha), while the rice crop surrounding the vegetables produced 96.1 kg grain (4.2 t/ha) and 139.1 kg straw (6.1 t/ha). Vegetable production from the

intercropped area was 307.1 kg (31.0 t/ha). Thus, the total food production with intercropping was 12.24 tons vs. 4.39 tons from the sole crop of rice, an increase in overall productivity of 170.8%. The study indicates a tremendous potential for increasing food production from wetland rice fields. The investigation is being continued on a large scale at Pattambi.

Machinery development & testing.

Manually operated diaphragm pump developed at BRRI

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(BRRI) has developed a manually operated diaphragm pump for low-cost irrigation. The pump has an average discharge capacity of 8,925 liters/hour and an optimum lifting head of 4.65 m (see table). It is made of steel sheets.

The cost of making one unit is roughly Tk 545 (US\$37) — low enough that poor

Upward movement of the handle causes the pump's diaphragm to expand and thus draw water from a well or a stream through a common manifold and into the pump chamber. Compression of the diaphragm forces the water from the chamber. Directional movement of water is controlled by a set of simple flapper valves on the inlet and outlet side.